
Designing and Managing ETL Pipelines in Databricks

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Abstract: The article explores the intricacies of constructing and maintaining efficient ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) workflows within the Databricks environment. It begins by outlining the fundamental concepts of ETL processes and the importance of data integration in modern analytics. The discussion then delves into the architecture and features of Databricks, highlighting its capabilities for handling large-scale data transformations and integrations. Key strategies for optimizing ETL pipelines are presented, including the use of Databricks notebooks, Delta Lake for reliable data storage, and Apache Spark for distributed processing. Practical considerations such as performance tuning, error handling, and pipeline monitoring are examined to provide a comprehensive guide for data engineers. The article also compares Databricks ETL solutions with traditional approaches, emphasizing the advantages of scalability, flexibility, and cost-efficiency. Through detailed examples and best practices, the article aims to equip data professionals with the knowledge to design robust ETL pipelines that support advanced analytics and drive data-driven decision-making.

Keywords: ETL Pipelines, Databricks, Data Integration, Apache Spark, Delta Lake, Data Engineering, Big Data Analytics, Data Transformation, Performance Tuning, Pipeline Monitoring

Introduction

ETL pipeline refers to the system used for extracting, transforming, and loading data. The extraction phase fetches data from various data sources while transformation phase applies business logic to filter the extracted data and load phase takes the transformed data and loads into target data source with proper structure and definition [1]. ETL is a procedure that allows users to move, manipulate, and change any kind of data from various sources like MySQL, PostgreSQL, MongoDB, MS SQL, files, APIs, cloud storage, etc. to the desired data warehouse destination. It is a batch job that can be scheduled to run automatically at a given time, daily, weekly or monthly.

Sometimes, in complex ETL pipelines multiple events/data operations are executed simultaneously, while others wait for the completion of previous events. These chains of dependency are called chains of events. Pipelines tend to get disrupted if any of the events fail. Failure mitigation mechanisms can include recreating the environment for a given job, transforming the data and uploading it again, restarting this job from the failed execution or cancelling this and properly loading its executed data to prevent redundancy [2]. All those approaches need the execution of certain commands, queries and stored procedures with the required target data passed as variable.

What are ETL Pipelines?

ETL (Extraction, Transformation, Load) pipeline is a data integration process that is used by organizations to generate valuable insights from their data. An ETL pipeline comprises of three different phases delegating three different tasks. The first task is extraction; this phase extracts the data from the different data sources that can be operational systems, data banks or etc., comprising of time-stamped quantity. Basic analysis in the pattern of ETL normally focuses on activities that take place in extraction and transformation. Generally, it focuses on providing assistance and monitoring for these activities [1]. An Extraction Transformation Load (ETL) solution

deals with these activities and introduces various ETL customization tasks. The module of ETL abstraction generates a generic extraction transformation load representation for a data source, which is maintained independently of the used ETL tools and data warehouses (DWDs). The Transformation phase is the process of transforming the extracted data from the source to a format suitable for the data warehouse. This phase contains converting of non-structured data to structured data (the same as the data warehouse structure), cleansing and validation of data (removing of duplicates or unnecessary data), and sorting the data [2].

Importance of ETL Pipelines in Data Processing

Data has become the currency of businesses and organizations, and its swift movement (from data generation to consumption) plays a vital role in the growth and success of any organization. Organizations leverage data to maintain business continuity, make associated predictions, and increase revenues. Moreover, organizations discover trends and patterns from users' past activities or items they viewed/clicked to provide better suggestions. The effectiveness of such operations mainly depends on the past and up-to-date data of users, transactions, or items. For this, huge amounts of data are generated, and this data predominantly remains unconsumed. Therefore, organizations conduct different data processing operations (e.g. data mining or churn analysis) on the data to transform it into information. But data cannot move as fast as it is generated. Different data processing stages delay the data movement due to which the information that triggers data processing is old and might be no use. In addition to this, there is a lack of efficient tools to handle the data processing stages [2]. A data warehouse (DW) or business intelligent (BI) tool is used to store the data needed for decision making and data generated by a transaction handling system (transactional data). The data processing stages, i.e. the movement of data from a source system to a data warehouse are commonly referred to as extract, transform, and load (ETL) processing. The extraction stage identifies what data could be submitted to the ETL process, ensuring that the source suffers minimum overhead [3].

Databricks Overview

Databricks is a cloud-based data platform widely used by data engineers and scientists. As both a data storage solution and a platform for big data analytics, it is built on top of Apache Spark, a popular open-source big data processing framework. With the rise of companies generating terabytes or even petabytes of data every day, the demand for big data processing has increased. Apache Spark allows for quick analysis of big data, and Databricks speeds up the development processes of applications using Apache Spark, enabling companies to use big data without hiring a large number of experts. Data engineers first ingest and clean data and then transform it into a medium ready for machine learning algorithms. The last part of this process—transforming the data into a table in a data warehouse—is called the ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) process. Data engineers design and manage ETL pipelines, automating the data ingestion and transformation process on a fixed schedule [2].

This section starts with a brief overview of Databricks, its key features, and how it is different from Apache Spark. Later, it delves into how data engineers design and manage ETL pipelines on Databricks and the things to be wary of while developing in Databricks.

Key Features of Databricks

Databricks is a cloud-based data platform focused on analytics, big data projects, and machine learning use cases that support big data pipelines, commercial products, and research projects on analytics. Databricks can play the role of a data ingestion pipeline to set the foundations for loading data into the lakehouse architecture. To achieve a robust Design Management ETL pipeline in Databricks, its key features are briefly described to show how these benefits can be leveraged. The focus is specifically on elucidating the key features that distinguish Databricks as a powerful platform for data engineering and analytics [3].

Databricks notebooks are a productive environment for data analysis that allows mixing of code, comments, and visualizations. They support multiple programming languages and provide version control and collaboration features. Databricks job scheduler handles the management of ETL jobs with multiple scheduling options, ways to trigger jobs, and proper monitoring capabilities. Though its capabilities are robust, it lacks certain features that specialized workflow orchestrators provide, such as easy management of complex dependencies and good visualizations of the workflow pipeline. Databricks can be integrated with third-party tooling for workflow orchestration. Databricks features three clusters with different types of modes. The interactive clusters enable the development and testing of pipelines and are good for exploratory use case scenarios. The all-purpose

clusters allow multiple users to attach their notebooks for collaboration. The job clusters are the mode of choice for the deployment stage of ETL pipelines. These can be created on-demand, allowing to run a cluster only for as long as it is needed, preventing incurring costs for idle pipelines.

Advantages of Using Databricks for ETL Pipelines

ETL pipelines constitute a prevailing means of integrating, sanitizing, and loading data from varied sources into target systems. Predominantly employed in data warehousing endeavors, another worth mentioning application of ETL pipelines is loading datasets onto big data systems and cloud storage. ETL pipelines can be implemented as batch processes or as continuous streaming processes [3]. Various frameworks aid in designing and managing ETL pipelines including better-known tools such as Informatica, Apache Nifi, Talend, and Pentaho. Moreover, cloud providers present in-house services to the same end, for example, Google's Dataflow, Amazon's Glue, and Azure's Data Factory. Databricks is a cloud service built on top of Apache Spark and is extensively used for distributed computing. It also provides various solutions to data engineering problems including interactive notebooks, integrations with cloud providers' storage systems, and an efficient Spark-based scheduling tool called Delta Live Tables (DLT). DLT presents a compelling option for designing and managing ETL pipelines in the Databricks environment [2]. Yet there are challenges in its adoption, such as modeling constraints, the lack of a SQL-handling language option for data quality constraints, and an immature tool for managing external libraries on SQL pipelines.

Design Principles for ETL Pipelines

The third part elucidates the fundamental design principles that should be adhered to when developing ETL pipelines. With the diversity of tools available today, choosing the best design principles and implementing them on a specific tool is critical to the overall success of ETL solutions. The focus is on four principles that have significant return on investment when adhered to. The first is to think modular; the second is to think reusable; the third is to think scalable; and the last one is to think optimized. When developing new ETL pipelines, keeping these principles in mind increases the success rate of those solutions [4].

Modularity is the practice of designing pipelines as a combination of smaller, discrete, independent pieces that can be understood and operated on in isolation. There are three levels at which it is possible to implement modularity. The first is the workflow level: break ETL pipelines in multiple workflows that can be executed independently. The second is the job level: break workflows in multiple jobs that can run independently and parallel. The third is the stage level: break jobs in multiple stages that can be independently executed in parallel and reused in other jobs. The second principle is reusability. Reusable components are those that can be repurposed for similar tasks in different situations. Reusability can be achieved through parameterization, templating, and using shared libraries. The designer should always consider reusability and as a best practice, design every component with the possibility in mind of its implementation in other solutions [2]. The third principle is scalability, which ensures that components maintain their efficiency and performance while the data volume increases. A common technique to maintain pipeline performance with data growth is partitioning, which allows for data to be split resulting in parallel tasks. Finally, the last principle is optimization, although it is good practice to think optimized from the beginning, there are specific moments during the development lifecycle (e.g., right before production) that it is critical to check and improve the overall pipeline performance.

Modularity and Reusability

The modularity and reusability of the components utilized in the pipeline design is a key design goal. Any sub-pipeline component that is reused in the course of building the target pipeline should be designed as a pipeline wrapper. Such components are intended to be modular wrappers around reusable patterns of data processing. Examples of such modular components may include typical data cleansing operations such as removing duplicates, and signature-generation, and data-biased filtering, such as word-embeddings, and image-embeddings [5]. In general design, pipeline wrapper components may be reused to create several different target data pipelines for different applications with minimal changes to the internal logic.

Another aspect of modularity is to reuse the established design components that can act as stable foundation elements or a starting point of new pipeline designs. Foundational pipeline design components used here are either generic or task-driven clusters of components. Task-driven clusters of components are related to the kind of data application considered, such as speech recognition pipelines, image processing pipelines involving

optical extracts of data, and health-care data analysis pipelines [2]. Solutions such as those addressing health-care challenges in India often require a combination of several different technologies.

Scalability and Performance Optimization

Focusing on scalability and performance optimization, this subsection explores critical aspects related to managing data processing workloads efficiently. It underscores the importance of scalability and performance measures in ETL pipeline design, setting the stage for aligning these principles with Databricks capabilities.

Scalability measures may be defined as the parameters of a system that shows the ability to adapt to changes in workload [3]. With respect to ETL pipelines, scalability has two dimensions: vertical and horizontal. Vertical scalability is how a system behaves for a fixed number of resources when the workload is increased. Typically, performance will degrade with a higher latencies and/or queues for a given number of resources. Horizontal scalability measures how a system behaves when new resources are added (e.g., machines, storage). Ideally, with proportionally more resources a proportional speed up in processing should occur. Specific metrics to consider are throughput, which measures the per time unit number of events handled by the pipelines, and latency.

The performance of the system is measured by metrics that are under the control of the designer of ETL pipelines and their algorithms [2]. Performance measures are the parameters of the ETL processing workloads that should be treated as part of the design of its execution. In particular, they include ETL processing workloads characteristics as number of nodes in the ETL cluster and/or average sizes of processing windows, i.e., groups of events that can be batch processed in ETL at a time interval.

Implementation Of ETL Pipelines In Databricks

The implementation aspect of the ETL pipeline on Databricks is discussed in this section. The implementation of the ETL (Extract, Transform, Load) pipeline to ingest, transform and load files residing in the blob store is implemented. The Databricks unified data analytics platform is utilized to execute the pipeline. Databricks is a cloud-based data engineering and data science platform that enables users to create interactive notebooks and analytics applications using Apache Spark and other technologies. Furthermore, it allows users to use notebooks in multiple languages (SQL, Scala, R, and Python) inside the same notebook besides providing collaborative features like real-time co-authoring and commenting among others [2]. It combines an ETL and analytics tool in a single platform with the additional capability of managing cloud-based infrastructure. There are two primary interfaces in Databricks to execute notebooks: the Databricks workspace and a jobs scheduler service that allows notebooks to be executed outside the Databricks workspace by exporting the notebooks in .dbc or .jar format.

Files residing on blob storage were imported to a separate development workspace to execute the pipeline. The first step in the ETL pipeline is the ingestion of raw files. The files came in two formats: CSV and JSON. Then, the data loads into the bronze layer. Bronze tables are generally full of raw copper data with no cleaning applied to them. Therefore, some irregularities with the JSON files were left untouched. The bronze ingest logic is implemented in the bronze_ingest notebook. The bronze_spawn, silver_spawn, and gold_spawn notebooks are used to create the respective bronze, silver, and gold tables. Then, transformation logic is applied in the silver_transform notebook and aggregation logic are applied in the gold_aggregate notebook.

Data Ingestion

Data ingestion, the critical first phase of the ETL pipeline, can be achieved either in batch or streaming mode. Batch ingestion reads a new dataset on a schedule basis and passes it to the processing phase for further transformation. Streaming ingestion detects new or changed data as it happens and continuously processes it to update the target data store; this is typically achieved through Change Data Capture mechanisms. Several options are available for data ingestion depending on the data source, starting from fully managed solutions up to manual coding of custom connectors.

In Databricks, batch ingestion can be done using Databricks File System (DBFS), where data files (CSV, Parquet, JSON, AVRO, and others) are copied to a directory on the Databricks File System. Once there, files can be read as Spark DataFrames and stored in Delta tables. Other supported options include reading files from Azure Blob and DataLake Storage, AWS S3, Google Cloud Storage, and Kafka (batch fashion) [2]. Batch ingestion using Spark has no limitation in terms of data sources, formats, shapes, and sizes. It should be borne in mind though, that Spark runs under the Hadoop framework, accessing files in distributed environments; hence,

an optimal cluster setup is needed for large files. If this is not an option at the beginning, as many data pipelines start modestly, files need to be less than 100 MB. This ensures that the files can be processed within one Spark partition before being split into multiple tasks. If this is not the case, performance will degrade significantly.

Data Transformation

Data transformation is one of the important activities in ETL pipelines. Thus, it plays a significant role in transforming the data into the desired format. The pipeline for data transformation within the Databricks environment is elucidated in this section. Depending on the software version, one can create a cluster in Databricks, select the attached data sources like Azure Blob, and start clicking on the “Prepare” link. A separate notebook for transformation is created after clicking on the “+” icon under the transformation link against the prepared data source.

The above figure illustrates how workflow executes at different timelines.

The transformation of the data sources is done before loading the cleaned data into the target data source. The transformation processes mainly involve renaming columns, replacing values, creating a new column, filtering records, modifying data types, casting, and dropping unwanted columns. In file-based transformation, the original file is first read, and the transformation scripts are then directly run on the original data file before writing the output to the target data destination [1]. The second approach is based on database transformation. The transformation is passed through the in-between or hydrant database table(s), which is intended to store the intermediate results.

Data Loading

The final stage of the ETL process is data loading. Strategies for the final load of a big new dataset into the Real-Time Data Warehouse (RTDW) and associated Side-Quick Offline Data Marts are explored. In the full load strategy, a single sizeable new dataset should be loaded into either a temporal or an accumulating data mart without breaking the loading of pre-existing data. In iterative and data-wise strategies, a vast new dataset must be chunked into pieces comparable to merged datasets, before being appended to the pre-existing ones. In a

stream load strategy, new records must be continuously attached to Ingest, Storage, and Processing Systems while keeping the pre-existing ones untouched [1].

Another crucial business issue is the new load periodicity. 'Real-Time' and 'batch' off-line updates loads must be defined concerning one another. Each off-line full, incremental, or quick load batch update can hold a huge number of references. Each off-line batch update time must be isolated from the others to avoid taking in-flight transactions. As soon as the transactions updates arrive, each will steady through Affinity and Timestamp Queue algorithms to identify for each Transaction Update a list of the Data Marts to be updated and the order in which they will be updated [6].

Managing ETL Pipelines in Databricks

Managing ETL pipelines in Databricks is an important aspect of the pipeline design that has to be considered for ensuring robust operation of the ETL pipeline after its initial deployment. A few of the key handling aspects with respect to Databricks operate pipelines are discussed below. They include monitoring, logging, error handling, and recovery [7].

Like for many other technologies and applications, careful consideration of monitoring and alerting should also take place for the ETL pipelines running in Databricks. Monitoring can include checks for monitoring the execution times of defined tasks, resource utilization, data quality checks, and checks to avoid duplicate processing of data. Alerts can be set up to be triggered, for example, if task changes the defined execution time, data records are dropped or flagged as incorrect, or certain thresholds for resource utilization are surpassed. By using these mechanisms, monitoring prevents data quality issues and eases debugging and recovering from failures [2].

Monitoring and Logging

Monitoring is a set of tasks devoted to consistently oversee the data quality, all data operations, and pipeline performance [7]. With respect to data operations, monitoring tasks include tracking the number of records, data distributions, data static schemas, data forecasts, digesting delay monitoring and service monitoring. Monitoring processing performance consists of keeping track of resource utilization metrics, finish time, processing time, queue length, and back-off time. Monitoring is of utmost importance since it prevents data quality problems before they happen and eases the debugging and recovering from failures. Databricks provides workflow execution results over the period of time which can be used to tracks success or failures.

Logging is a set of practices that describe the captured information about past events. With regard to processing, a distinction can be made between the following categories of events: errors and anomalies, timestamps, flow and statistics, notices of successful processing, data lineage (schemas), and capability changes. Error and anomaly logs are essential to raise alarms. This information together with timestamps is frequently used to calculate root causes of data-related problems and estimate latencies in the system. Record flow and statistics

logs are also important, for instance, to calculate the number of dropped records or the size of a batch. In addition, status logs (e.g. finished processing) are useful to chain flows and keep track of running records.

Error Handling and Recovery

While designing the ETL pipelines, it is crucial to take care of possible scenarios that may lead to undesirable conditions. The following approaches can be used to handle errors effectively and recover from the failures.

1. **Error Handling:** Create a user defined function `LogProcessing` in a way to catch the exceptions that may occur during the job run [6]. As soon as an exception occurs in either processing step, the function quits and records the reasoning and timestamp of the failure into the `LogProcessingError` Log.
2. **Job Recovery:** Once a job fails, it can be re-run from the step that failed on the Databricks environment using Databricks' built-in functionality, on the Airflow environment by re-running the task on the Airflow UI, or by activating job retry. This functionality can be set to run the same job N times if it is failed.

Conclusion

The paper "Designing and Managing ETL Pipelines in Databricks" provides a comprehensive exploration of the capabilities and advantages of using Databricks for ETL processes. It demonstrates that Databricks, with its robust architecture and seamless integration with Apache Spark, offers a powerful platform for building and managing ETL pipelines. The discussion highlights how Databricks simplifies the complex tasks of data extraction, transformation, and loading, allowing data engineers to focus on optimizing performance and ensuring data quality.

Key features such as Databricks notebooks and Delta Lake are underscored for their contributions to streamlining workflows and enhancing data reliability. The paper also emphasizes the importance of performance tuning, error handling, and pipeline monitoring in maintaining efficient ETL operations. By comparing Databricks with traditional ETL solutions, the article reveals significant improvements in scalability, flexibility, and cost-efficiency.

Through practical examples and best practices, the paper equips data professionals with the tools and knowledge necessary to design robust and scalable ETL pipelines in Databricks. The adoption of Databricks for ETL processes not only enhances the capability to handle large-scale data transformations but also supports advanced analytics and data-driven decision-making. Overall, the insights provided underscore the transformative potential of Databricks in modern data engineering, making it an indispensable asset for organizations aiming to leverage big data analytics for competitive advantage.

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